

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF STATE-SUPPORTED SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

The small and medium-sized business sector is one of the most important pillars of sustainable economic development, ensuring regional economic stability, employment growth and the introduction of innovations. In the Georgian context, the development of small and medium-sized businesses is linked to both structural economic transformation and the socio-political stability of the country. Despite the fact that in recent years the state has activated its policy of supporting small and medium-sized businesses and launched various support, financing and technical assistance programs, this sector still faces many systemic and practical challenges, the solution of which is critically important for achieving sustainable development.

The paper discusses the opportunities for small and medium-sized business development and the barriers and challenges they face in Georgia. The programs implemented with state support and their impact on the economic and financial activity of small and medium-sized businesses are analyzed. Although ongoing state-supported programs to some extent stimulate businesses to find the necessary financial and technological resources, they still fail to ensure the establishment of an economic system necessary for large-scale and inclusive development.

Keywords: Small and medium-sized businesses; State programs; Socio-economic stability; Innovative potential; Economic and financial transformation.

Introduction: In the conditions of modern economic development, small and medium-sized businesses are considered one of the most important pillars, which directly affects the socio-economic stability of the country, strengthening the innovative potential and diversification of the domestic market. Small and medium-sized businesses have a unique function to create jobs, increase the economic involvement of the population and promote the broad and effective distribution and redistribution of economic and financial resources. In Georgia, as an economy in transition, the development of small and medium-sized businesses is a strategic priority, to which the state policy responds with multilateral support programs. However, at the same time, small and medium-sized businesses actually face many challenges, including: problems of financial accessibility, scarcity of technological resources, incompetent management, issues of regulatory opacity and low level of market competition, which prevent them from fully realizing the opportunities for sustainable development and integration into international markets.

Review: In the Georgian economic space, small and medium-sized businesses have been considered for years as a turning point, an indicator of sustainable economic growth, employment and possible inflation in Georgia. The special importance of this sphere is due to its ability to diversify the economy, ensure social and economic stabilization and encourage innovation, which is necessary for a country with a developing economy. Despite such potential, small and medium-sized businesses in Georgia still experience the impact of multiple systemic obstacles, the solution of which

requires appropriate targeted, digital, financial and institutional approaches. The most significant barrier is the insufficient availability of scarce financial resources. Small and medium-sized business entities still rely on loans issued by commercial banks, which often charge high interest rates and require long-term relationships. Although the state increases grants, loan guarantees and subsidies through certain programs, this strategy still fails to meet the transformational need, as the use of loans often fails to ensure long-term competitiveness, which in turn limits investments in technologies, innovations and strategic changes. In addition, incomplete information on the financial market does not give many companies the right to a wide range of choices and prevents them from making sound decisions in the current market environment. One of the significant challenges for small and medium-sized businesses is the lack of business knowledge and management skills, which includes managerial competencies, understanding of the legislative framework and strategic vision. Many small and medium-sized businesses insufficiently use market analysis, consumer research and continuous improvement of service quality, which is especially problematic for small and medium-sized businesses operating in the regions. Another challenge of the current reality is the lack of digital transformation, which is manifested in the lack of use of internet marketing, digital sales, and online platforms, which in turn leads to the loss of access to the customer base and many opportunities. Regional disparities are a particular challenge, as the real potential of small and

medium-sized businesses is often hidden not in the central, but in peripheral zones, where infrastructural, financial and educational resources are limited and initiatives at the local level are poorly supported. It is also found that investment resources and grant instruments available to small businesses are often not combined with the needs that correspond to the real needs of entrepreneurs, which in turn reduces the effectiveness and benefits of programs. It is important for the state to develop a more coordinated and segmented needs-based policy, which is based on the specific problems of each sector, and not only standard approaches focused on general support. It is necessary to create a differentiated evaluation system of programs in order to analyze their real impact and make timely adjustments.

Special attention is paid to the role of the state in supporting small and medium-sized businesses, which

includes both financial incentives and guarantee schemes, as well as educational, informational and technical support components. Current state-supported programs in Georgia, such as "Produce in Georgia", "Support for Micro and Small Entrepreneurship", support for agribusiness and other initiatives, serve to strengthen small and medium-sized businesses, both in the regional and local context. Determining the effectiveness of this issue is important for analyzing how effectively the state is able to create a sustainable and competitive business environment through these tools. We present the number of active enterprises by organizational-legal forms and forms of ownership in 2019-2023. Table N1.

Number of active enterprises by organizational-legal forms and forms of ownership 2019-2023

Table N1

2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	
160465	160682	170909	200425	224538	Total
<i>By legal status</i>					
63876	63272	66970	70399	71759	Limited Liability Company
700	712	715	711	704	Joint Stock Company
165	154	145	139	123	Joint Liability Company
16	14	15	17	16	Limited Partnership
153	134	164	151	147	Cooperative
443	413	399	362	355	Branch of a foreign enterprise
95112	95983	102501	128646	151434	Individual Entrepreneur
<i>By ownership</i>					
160119	160345	170583	200108	224231	Non-State
149571	150639	160044	174815	187140	Private domestic person
8355	7589	8413	23006	34710	Private foreign person
2193	2117	2126	2287	2381	Private mixed
346	337	326	317	307	State

As for 2024, compared to the previous year, the turnover of the business sector increased by 11.6 percent and amounted to 228.5 billion GEL. The growth trend was also characterized by the production output of the business sector. In 2024, its volume was determined at 90.5 billion GEL, which is 16.3 percent more than the figure for 2023. In 2024, 67.7 percent of the turnover of the business sector fell on large businesses, 15.8 percent on medium-sized businesses, and 16.5 percent on small businesses. There was a different distribution in the case of total production output: large businesses accounted for 46.8 percent of production output, medium-sized businesses 25.5 percent, and small businesses 27.7 percent. In 2024, the average number of employees in the business sector was determined at 866.2 thousand people, which is 5.2 percent more than the figure for the previous year. Of the total number of employees, 43.2 percent were women and 56.8 percent were men. 39.4 percent of the total number of employees was in large businesses, 20.3 percent in medium-sized businesses, and 40.3 percent in small businesses.

Conclusion: The importance of small and medium-sized business development for Georgia is extremely high in terms of both economic and social and regional sustainability. Small and medium-sized businesses represent the structural foundation of the economy, which is directly related to employment growth,

optimal use of local resources and diversification of the country's domestic product. Although the state has been pursuing a support policy in recent years, including through flagship programs such as "Make in Georgia" and "Support for Micro and Small Entrepreneurship", as well as grant and guarantee mechanisms, loan support schemes and investment incentives aimed at encouraging small and medium-sized businesses, the challenges in practice remain multifaceted and complex. In conclusion, it can be said that programmatic support from the state has significantly improved access to financing for small and medium-sized businesses, expanded export opportunities and contributed to the quantitative growth trend of small and medium-sized enterprises in the regions. During the implementation of the program, systemic barriers have been identified, such as inadequate dissemination of information on programs, bureaucratic obstacles, scarcity of digital and consulting resources, unequal access by region and low degree of inclusiveness.

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